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Title : STEP-UP: The Making of a Marian Leader

Proponents : Dr. Ma. Cristeta M. Aduca, Mrs. Ruby Lyn R. Nuestro, Dr. John G. Tayaban, Miss Kristine Anne Israel, Rpm, RGC

Abstract

This research is conducted to determine the career stage of school leaders under the five (5) domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPS-SH) and school leader's professional practice using the Success Competencies of Southeast Asian School Heads. The researchers considered the Descriptive survey as most applicable method in order to determine the school leader's career stage and practice. A questionnaire as the main instrument was then given to the school leaders in order to gather the data needed. It revealed in the frequency distribution of School Leader Respondent's Profile the following: age, majority of the respondents belong to 41-50 years of age, female, whose educational attainment belongs to those with Master's Degree, mostly from the tertiary level, five and below years of experience as school leader and have attended seminars or trainings on leadership/management. It further revealed that the school leaders are in career stage 2, particularly on the following domains: Leading Strategically, Managing School Operations and Resources, Focusing on Teaching and Learning, and Building connections. For Developing self and others domain, school leaders are categorized in career stage 3. As to the school leader's professional practice, they can do well in their leadership roles and responsibilities. However, they need to develop more in some aspects of the leadership responsibilities on the areas of financial management and strategic thinking and innovation. It is vital to engage school heads to actively embrace a continuing effort to attain high levels of proficiency through a leadership developmental formation.

Keywords: school leadership, professional development, instructional leadership, leadership formation

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Introduction

To better prepare children for the higher educational demands of life and work in the 21st century, many countries around the world are undertaking wide-ranging reforms. What skills do young people need in this rapidly changing world and what competencies do teachers need to effectively teach those skills? What teacher preparation and continuing professional development are needed to prepare graduates to teach well in a 21st century classroom? What roles and responsibilities should 21st century school leaders possess? (Farmer, 2010). These questions demand that educational institutions rethink many aspects of their education systems such as the quality of recruiting systems, the type of education teacher applicants obtain before they start working, how they are monitored and what education and support they get, how their compensation is structured, and how to improve performance of struggling teachers and enhance development among the best ones. These changes have profound implications for the leadership of schools, education systems, teachers, and the teaching and learning process. In the past, the focus is the teachers' delivery of wisdom. Today, the challenge is how to foster user-generated wisdom among teachers in the frontline. In the past, different students were taught in similar ways. Today, teachers are expected to embrace diversity with differentiated pedagogical practices. The kind of teaching needed today requires teachers to be high-level knowledge workers who constantly advance their own professional knowledge as well as that of their profession. To develop knowledge workers, education systems need to transform the leadership and work organization of their schools to an environment in which professional norms of management complement bureaucratic and administrative forms of control.

Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act 2001, defines a school head as "a person responsible for administrative and instructional supervision of a school or cluster of schools" (Section 4). School heads have the authority, responsibility and accountability for taking care of people in schools (people effectiveness) while maximizing organizational performance and health (school effectiveness) by setting the direction of schools, managing their systems and processes, promoting quality teaching and learning, nurturing themselves and others and engaging stakeholders in initiatives towards the improvement of school communities. The role of the school leader has grown far beyond that of administrator designing curricula and managing resources. Developing school leaders requires clearly defining their responsibilities, providing access to appropriate professional development throughout their careers, and acknowledging their pivotal role in improving school and student performance. Darling-Hammond, LaPointe, Meyerson, Orr and Cohen (2007) indicated that the role of school leaders in developing high performing schools has been increasingly recognized by policymakers and practitioners. A growing attention on the pivotal role of school leaders in improving the quality of education is now evident. This recognition coupled with a growing shortage of high quality leaders has heightened interest in leadership development as a major reform strategy. Understanding the scope of challenge faced by leaders of today's schools is critical inasmuch as contemporary school leaders play

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overwhelming array of roles ranging from educational visionaries and change agents to instructional leaders, curriculum and assessments experts, budget analysts, facility managers, special program administrators and community builders. These aspects of school leaders' roles demand that they not only possess the capacity to develop strong instruction but also sophisticated understanding of organizations and organizational change. In order for the quality of education to be raised and sustained to the level of excellence and inasmuch as highly skilled school leaders are not born (Southern Regional education Board, n.d.), it is essential that school leaders are equipped with appropriate competencies. Likewise, it is also important that school leaders regard managing or leading a school a valued profession. School heads as key leaders in an educational system are indispensable in achieving the school's goal to provide quality education.

In 2003, the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization Regional Center for Educational Innovation and Technology (SEAMEO INNOTECH) developed the Competency Framework for Southeast Asian School Heads. The competency framework was envisioned to provide a common foundation for defining what skills and attributes are needed of school heads in order to effectively carry out their roles, and lead their schools to excellence and success. Ten years after, SEAMEO INNOTECH undertook the challenge of reviewing and updating the competency framework to make sure that it remains responsive to the changing contexts and needs of school heads as well as the communities they serve. Accordingly, a consultative and participatory process that spanned nine months (October 2012 and February to September 2013) and covered 9 countries (Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam) was undertaken. The result is the Competency Framework for Southeast Asian School Heads (2014 Edition) comprised of five competency domains, 16 general competencies, 42 enabling competencies, and 170 indicators. The competency framework is intended to be a basis for the development of SEAMEO INNOTECH's capacity-building initiatives for Southeast Asian school heads. It does not replace, but rather complements, existing regional and national standards.

With the implementation of K-12 Basic Education Program and the Philippines Professional Standards for Teachers, there is a need for DepEd to complement these reforms by ensuring that the current set of standards for school heads is K-12 aligned and internationally comparable, leading to the development of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads. The Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads, which is aligned with local and international frameworks, complements the reform initiatives on teacher and school leader qualities as it addresses career stages for professional development. It articulates what constitutes school leadership quality through well-defined domains, strands, and indicators that provide measures of professional learning, competent practice, and effective leadership and management. The Department of Education use these professional standards as basis in the crafting of trainings and development plans for school heads. Clearly, the role of school heads as stewards of schools is crucial in ensuring an enabling and supportive environment for effective teaching and learning to happen.

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According to Kadir (2019), effective management of education depends on the availability and management of resources, accountability and participatory decision-making (good governance) towards the realization of educational goals. Similarly, Nidadhavolu(2019) stated the leaders should encourage and motivate their subordinates to perform exceptionally, which will ensure job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Effective principals are strong educators, anchoring their work on central issues of learning and teaching and continuous school improvement. Moreover, according to Schmoker (2016), the combination of three concepts constitutes the foundation for positive improvement results: meaningful teamwork; clear, measurable goal; and the regular collection and analysis of performance data. The school leaders, especially the principal, had a critical impact on the development of the school's teacher culture via their determination and encouragement. Both the school principal and the school's senior teachers played an exemplary and leading role in shaping a high-quality school culture for professional development. As explained by Wallace (2013), effective principals perform five key practices well such as shaping a vision of academic success for all students; Creating a climate hospitable to education; cultivating leadership in others; Improving instruction; Managing people, data and processes to foster school improvement. According to Cisler (2017), team leader as the most important role, while supervisor was rated as the least important. A principal should work cooperatively with staff to ensure more effective use of their skills. While, the task of a principal in making decisions on staff development programs was not necessarily expected by the practicing teachers.

The framework of this study is anchored on Contingency Management Theory which posited that no one management approach suits every organization. There are several external and internal factors that will ultimately affect the chosen management approach. The contingency theory identifies their variables that are likely to influence an organization's structure: the size of an organization, technology being employed, and style of leadership. Fred Fiedler, the theorist behind the contingency management theory, proposed that the traits of a leader were directly related to how effectively he led. According to Fiedler's theory, there are set of leadership traits handy for every kind of situation. It means that a leader must be flexible enough to adapt to the changing environment. The contingency management theory can be summed up as follows: Theory X and Theory Y: do you believe that every individual gets maximum satisfaction from the work they do? Or are you of the opinion that some view work as a burden and only do it for the money? Such assumptions influence how an organization is run. The assumptions also form the basis of Theory X and Theory Y. Douglas McGregor is the theorist credited with developing these two contrasting concepts. More specifically, these theories refer to two management styles: the authoritarian (Theory X) and participative (Theory Y). In an organization where team members show little passion for their work, leaders are likely to employ the authoritarian style of management. But if employees demonstrate a willingness to learn and are enthusiastic about what they do, their leader is likely to use participative management. The management style that a manager adapts will influence just how well he can keep his team members motivated. Theory X holds a pessimistic view of employees in the sense that they cannot work in the

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absence of incentives. Theory Y, on the other hand, holds an optimistic opinion of employees. The latter theory proposes that employees and managers can achieve a collaborative and trust-based relationship. Still, there are a couple of instances where theory X can be applied. For instance, large corporations that hire thousands of employees for routine work may find adapting this form of management ideal.

It is in this premise that this research was conducted to prepare Marian school leaders to assume their positions and perform their responsibilities efficiently and effectively. It aimed to investigate the leadership practices of Marian school leaders. In this study, the profile of the school leaders in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, school level, position/rank, number of years as school leader, seminars/trainings attended on leadership/management were determined. This study also explored the assessment of the school leaders' professional practice as regards to leading strategically, managing school operations and resources, focusing on teaching and learning, developing self and others, and building connections as well as their career stage. The results of the assessment were used as basis for the crafting of a proposed Leadership Formation Program for school leaders of Saint Mary's University.

Methodology

This research used the descriptive research method to determine the professional practice and career stage of the school leaders of Saint Mary's University. The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. SMU is one of the five CICM schools in the Philippines founded in 1928 and earned its university status in 1994. SMU carries on the mission of integral human development by joyfully witnessing to Christ's mission, responsibly taking the lead and participating in community building, relentlessly manifesting academic, personal and professional excellence, conscientiously strengthening communion, and steadfastly nurturing creativity and physical prowess. The respondents of the study were the academic leaders of Saint Mary's University from the Basic Education to the Graduate school levels namely: Learning Area Coordinators and Principals of the Basic Education Unit ; the Academic Coordinators, Department Heads and Deans of the Tertiary Education Unit and the Graduate School Program Heads and the Dean of the Graduate School for school year 2022-2023. They were selected purposively as they were the current academic school leaders of Saint Mary's University. The tool used in gathering the data was a survey questionnaire. The first part determined the profile of the school leaders; the second part assessed the career stage of the academic school leaders using the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads and third part determined the leadership practices of academic school leaders using the Success Competencies of Southeast Asian School Heads. The Philippine Professional Standards for School heads was contextualized to align it to the Philosophy, vision-mission of the university. The Philippine Professional Standards for school Heads introduced a continuum of professional practice that supported school heads to pursue career progression amid various national and international reforms such as the K to 12 Basic Education Program and the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads

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as well as ASEAN Integration, globalization, and the changing character of the 21st century learners. The tool was composed of five (5) domains: Leading Strategically, Managing School Operations and Resources, Focusing on Teaching and Learning, Developing Self and Others and Building Connections. These five domains collectively comprised 34 strands that refer to specific dimensions of school leadership practices. After seeking the consent of the participants in this research, a google form of the questionnaire was uploaded for those who wished to answer electronically. A hard copy was distributed individually to those who opted to answer in paper. The researchers strictly observed the following ethical considerations including objectivity and integrity, respect of the research subjects' right to privacy and dignity and protection of subjects from personal harm, presentation of research findings, and misuse of research role. The data collected underwent the process of data analysis. Percentage, frequency distribution, and weighted mean were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents and the professional practice and career stage of the school leaders.

Results and Discussions

Profile of the School Leaders

Majority of the respondents belonged to the age group of 41-50 years old. Most of them were females, and were school and department leaders from the tertiary level (50.0%). In terms of educational attainment, most of them were department heads and have Master's degree. With regard to the years of their leadership experience, majority of them have 1-5 years experience as a leader. Lastly, most of the respondents were able to attend seminars on leadership/management.

Career stage of the school leaders

Leading strategically

Almost half or 50% of the respondents are in career stage 2 in terms of the following sub-domains: (1) Vision, Mission and Core Values (Serve as a role model in the school and the wider school community in embodying the SMU vision, mission and core values to sustain shared understanding and alignment of school policies and programs, projects and activities); (2) School Planning and Implementation (Develop and implement with the planning team school plans aligned with the institutional goals and policies); (3) Policy Implementation and Review (Undertake policy implementation and review in the school to ensure that operations are consistent with national and local laws, regulations and issuances); (4) Research and Innovation (Utilize relevant research findings from reliable sources in facilitating data-driven and evidence based innovations to improve school performance); (5) Program Design and Implementation (Implement programs in the school that support the development of learners); (6) Learner Voice (Utilize learner voice, such as feelings, views and or opinions to inform policy development and decision-making towards

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school development); (6) Monitoring and Evaluation processes and tools (Utilize available monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement).

Managing school operations and resources

In terms of managing school operations and resources, the school leaders manifested traits of category (2) leaders as shown in the following statements: (1) Records Management (Manage school data and information using technology and ICT to ensure efficient and school operations); (3) Management and Staff (Manage staffing such as teaching load distribution and grade level and subject area assignment in adherence to laws, policies and guidelines and issuances based on the needs of the school); (3) Financial Management (Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of policies, guidelines and issuances in managing finances such as allocation, procurement, disbursement and liquidation aligned with the school plan; Manage finances adhering to policies, guidelines and issuances in allocation, procurement, disbursement and liquidation aligned with the school plan); (4) Emerging Opportunities and Challenges (Managing emerging opportunities and challenges to encourage equality in addressing the needs of the learners, school personnel and stakeholders). However, the school leaders showed traits of Category leader as manifested in the following domains: (1) School Facilities and Equipment (Establish shared accountability in managing school facilities and equipment in adherence to policies, guidelines and issuances on acquisition, recording, utilization, repair and maintenance, storage and disposal); (2) School Safety Disaster preparedness, mitigation and resiliency (Work with the wider school community in managing school safety and disaster preparedness, mitigation and resiliency to maintain continuous delivery of instruction);

Focusing on Teaching and Learning

In terms of focusing on teaching and learning, the school leaders exhibited traits of category (2) leaders as presented in the following sub-domains: (1) School-based review, contextualization and implementation of learning strategies (Work with teams in conduct of review, contextualization and implementation on learning standards to assist teachers in making the curriculum ready for learners); (3) Teacher Performance Feedback (Use validated feedback obtained from learners, parents and other stakeholders to help teachers improve their performance; Collaborate with school personnel in effectively using validated feedback obtained from learners, parents and other stake holders to help their teachers improve their performance); (4) Career Awareness and Opportunities (Undertake initiatives in integrating career awareness and opportunities in the provision of learning experiences aligned with the curriculum); (5) Learner Discipline (Ensure that learner discipline policies developed with stakeholders are integrated to various school processes and are applied consistently at all times, by all school personnel at all levels.

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However, the school leaders exhibited traits of category 2 leaders as shown in the following sub-domains: (1) Teaching Standards and Pedagogy (Provide technical assistance to teachers on teaching standards and pedagogies within and across learning areas to improve their teaching practice) (2) Learner Achievement and other performance indicators (Utilize learning outcomes in developing data-based interventions to maintain learner achievement and attain other performance indicators); (3) Learning Assessment (Provide technical assistance to teachers in using learning assessment tools, strategies and results consistent with curriculum requirements to ensure accountability achieving higher learning outcomes);

Developing self and others

In terms of developing self and others, the school leaders manifested traits of category 3 leaders as presented in the following sub-domains: (1) Personal and Professional Development (Reflect on the attainment of personal and professional development goals and objectives based on the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads); (2) Performance Management (Monitor and evaluate with school personnel the implementation of performance management system to ensure career advancement for individual school personnel to improve office performance).

However, the school leaders also manifested category 2 as reflected in the following sub-domains: (1) Reflect on the attainment of personal and professional development goals and objectives based on the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (Apply professional reflection and learning to improve one's practices); (2) Apply professional reflection and learning to improve one's practices (Participate in professional networks to upgrade knowledge and skills to enhance practice); (3) Professional development of school personnel (Implement professional development initiatives to enhance strengths and address performance gaps among school personnel); (4) Leadership development in individual teams (Provide opportunities to individuals and teams in performing leadership roles and responsibilities); (5) General welfare of human resources (Implement laws, policies, guidelines and issuances on the rights, privileges and benefits of school personnel to ensure their general welfare); (6) Rewards and recognition mechanism (Implement a school rewards system to recognize and motivate learners, school personnel and other stakeholders for exemplary performance and or continued support).

Building connections

In terms of building connections, the school leaders have shown traits of category 2 leaders as exhibited in the following sub-domains: (1) Management of diverse relationships (Demonstrate skills in dealing with authorities, colleagues, parents and stakeholders to encourage an enabling and supportive environment for learners); (2) Management of school organizations (Manage school organizations, such as learner organizations, faculty clubs and parent-teachers associations, by applying relevant policies and guidelines to support the attainment of institutional goals; Evaluate the accomplishment of the school organizations,

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such as learner organizations, faculty clubs and parent-teacher organizations, to determine the impact on the attainment of institutional goals); (3) Inclusive Practice (Exhibit inclusive practices, such as gender sensitivity, physical and mental health awareness and culture responsiveness, to foster awareness, acceptance and respect); (4) Communication (Communicate effectively in speaking and in writing to teachers, learners, parents and stakeholders, through positive use of communication platforms, to facilitate information sharing, collaboration and support); Community Engagement (Initiate partnerships with the community, such as parents, alumni, authorities, industries and other stakeholders, to strengthen support for learner development as well as school community improvement).

School leader’s extent of professional practice on strategic thinking and innovation

In terms of the school leaders’ extent of professional practice on strategic thinking and innovation domain, school leaders practice charting the direction of the school satisfactorily. They have started to work with the school and community stakeholders in developing a school strategic plan (M=2.34) and lead in the implementation of the strategic plan (M=2.34), but they need to learn more. This is expected since majority of the school leaders are new in their positions with 1-5 years of experience. However, they can do well in demonstrating the school’s vision and model the values in everyday work and practice (M=2.97). This is remarkably a sign that they have imbibed the values espoused by the university. When making informed decisions, school leaders have also started to use a range of evidence to support, monitor, evaluate, and improve the strategic (M=2.44) and practice regular review of the plan/program implementation and utilize results in addressing implementation concerns and issues (M=2.41), but need to learn more. Finally, in leading change and innovation, school leaders can do well in sustaining creativity and innovation in school programs to achieve higher learning outcomes (M=2.53) but needs to learn more in leading the change process toward the development and implementation of new approaches, systems, and structures(M=2.38). Overall, school leaders have a satisfactory professional practice on strategic and innovation domain but still need to learn more about it.

School leader’s extent of professional practice on managerial leadership

In terms of managing school resources and systems, school leaders can do well in managing the learning environment (M=2.72) and systems and procedures (M=2.63) but need to learn more in managing financial resources (M=2.38). In managing staff performance, school leaders can do well in managing school personnel (M=2.63), support professional development of staff (M=2.75), and recognize staff performance (M=2.88). Lastly, in managing sustainable, school leaders can also do well in demonstrating program and project management skills (M=2.59) and promoting school-based programs and projects that support sustainable development (M=2.75). Overall, school leaders are very satisfactory on managerial leadership domain.

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School leader's extent of professional practice on instructional leadership

In terms of leading curriculum implementation and improvement, school leaders can do well in managing curriculum implementation (M=2.94) and promoting sensitivity towards diversity and differentiated instruction (M=2.88). In creating a learner-centered environment, school leaders can do well in promoting learner-centered activities (M=3.06), promoting a healthy, safe, and inclusive learning environment (M=3.19), and promoting a culture of peace and respect for diversity (M=3.13). Likewise, school leaders can do well in supervising and evaluating teachers' performance, as well as in applying appropriate models to supervision and evaluation (M=3.06) and nurturing teacher-leaders (M=3.03). Lastly, in terms of delivering planned learning outcomes, school leaders can do well in promoting team-based approaches (M=2.78) and managing assessments to improve teaching and learning (M=2.91). Overall, school leaders are satisfactory in their professional practice on instructional leadership domain.

School leader's extent of professional practice on personal excellence

With regard to managing personal effectiveness, school leaders can do well in leading by example (M=3.25), demonstrating transparency and accountability (M=3.22), practicing a balanced, healthy lifestyle (M=2.88), taking pride in one's profession (M=3.38), and in delivering results (M=3.16). Also, they can do well in acting on challenges and possibilities, managing priorities (M=2.94), exhibiting decisiveness in addressing challenges (M=2.84), and exhibiting an enterprising attitude (M=2.75). Lastly, in pursuing continuous professional development, school leaders can do well in taking responsibility for one's own lifelong learning (M=3.03) and advocating ASEAN values and perspectives (M=2.69). Generally, school leaders can do well in their professional practice along personal excellence domain.

School leader's extent of professional practice on stakeholder engagement

In promoting shared responsibility for school improvement, school leaders can do well in building trust and leading teams/communities for school improvement (M=2.81) and empowering the community to work for the enhancement of school performance (M=2.75). School leaders have very satisfactory practice of managing education alliances and networks, communicating effectively with different stakeholders (M=2.69), facilitating school community partnerships and activities (M=2.69), promoting consensus-building (M=2.56) and managing conflict and practice negotiation skills (M=2.59). Lastly, in sustaining collaborative relationships with stakeholders, school leaders can do well in supporting community-based programs and projects (M=2.97) and communicating school performance to stakeholders (M=2.81). Overall, school leaders can do well in their professional practice along stakeholder engagement domain.

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Conclusions and Recommendations

In the light of the findings, this study concludes that the school leaders are in Career Stage 2 in their professional development as leaders. They apply the required knowledge and understanding of the authority, responsibility, and accountability expected of them as described in the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads. They are professionally independent in performing their functions as instructional leaders and administrative managers. They maintain school effectiveness and people effectiveness by leading strategically, managing school operations and resources, focusing on teaching and learning, developing themselves and others, and building connections. They reflect on their practices for improvement and seek to involve all school personnel in professional learning and career advancement. The school leaders can do well in their professional practice of their leadership roles and responsibilities. However, they need to learn more in some aspects of their leadership responsibilities on the areas of financial management and strategic thinking and innovation.

Considering the conclusions drawn, this study hereby recommends the need to set out clear expectations of school heads along well-defined career stages of professional development from beginning to exemplary practice. It is also vital to engage school heads to actively embrace a continuing effort to attain high levels of proficiency through a leadership developmental formation, and provide support for professional learning and development, help identify development needs, and facilitate a performance-based assessment of school leaders. Lastly, the proposed plan for a developmental leadership formation program for Marian School leaders: GABAY be conscientiously conducted.

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